

Potentiometric Studies on Some Ternary Complexes of Nd(III), Sm(III), Gd(III) and Ho(III) with Cyclohexanediaminetetraacetic Acid as Primary Ligand

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Manuscript received 2 January 1981, revised 17 April 1982, accepted 12 November 1982

The formation constants of the ternary complexes of neodymium(III), samarium(III), gadolinium(III) and holmium(III) with cyclohexanediaminetetraacetic acid (CyDTA) as primary ligand and dihydroxynaphthalene (DHN), dihydroxynaphthalene-6-sulphonic acid (DHNSA) and catechol-3,5-disulphonic acid (CDSA) as secondary ligands have been investigated by potentiometric titration technique. The values of formation constants of 1:1:1 ternary chelates are reported at three different temperatures, and at a fixed ionic strength, $\mu=0.1 M$ (NaClO_4).

IN continuation of the earlier report from this laboratory^{1,2} on the application of Irving-Rossotti titration technique for the study of the ternary complexes of some rare earths, results on the study of the systems MAL, where M=Nd(III), Sm(III), Gd(III) or Ho(III); A=cyclohexanediaminetetraacetic acid (CyDTA) and L=dihydroxynaphthalene (DHN), dihydroxynaphthalene-6-sulphonic acid, sodium salt (DHNSA) or catechol-3,5-disulphonic acid, disodium salt (CDSA) are presented in this paper. The formation constants, $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$, have been determined at 5, 25 and 45° and at ionic strength, $\mu=0.1 M$ (NaClO_4).

Recently, the rare earth ions have been reported to expand their coordination number to larger than six^{3,4}. The assumption of a coordination number of eight for all these rare earths seems to explain the experimental observations more satisfactorily than a coordination number of six in case of $[M(\text{III})-(\text{CyDTA})(L)]^{3-}$ systems, as reported in this paper.

Experimental

Materials : The stock solutions of 0.02M of rare earth metal chlorides (I. R. E. Ltd.) were prepared by dissolving the calculated quantities in perchloric acid and their metal contents were estimated by complexometric titrations⁵. A stock solution of 0.01 M of disodium salt of CyDTA (Koch-light) was prepared by dissolving the calculated amount of the acid in the required volume of standardized sodium hydroxide solution. The stock solutions of 0.01 M DHNSA (Koch-light) and CDSA (Loba-chemie) were prepared in double distilled water. A stock solution of 0.01 M DHN (Fluka) was prepared in purified dioxane. All other solutions were made from their AR grade samples. The details of the instruments used are the same as described earlier¹.

Procedure : For the study of ternary complexes the following four mixtures were prepared,

- (A) $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ perchloric acid.
- (B) $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ perchloric acid + $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ secondary ligand.
- (C) $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ perchloric acid + $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ primary ligand + $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ metal.
- (D) $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ perchloric acid + $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ primary ligand + $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ metal + $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ secondary ligand.

In each case the total volume was made upto 100 ml and ionic strength was maintained at 0.1 M by adding appropriate amount of neutral sodium perchlorate solution. In case of DHN, 50% aqueous-dioxane medium was used, as the ligand is insoluble in aqueous medium. In all these cases the ratio of metal to primary ligand to secondary ligand was kept at 1:1:1. These mixtures were titrated against standard NaOH using pH-meter. All titrations were carried out in nitrogen atmosphere at three different temperatures. A typical plot of pH against volume of alkali added have been represented in Fig. 1 for $[\text{Sm}(\text{III})-(\text{CyDTA})(\text{DHNSA})]^{3-}$ system. The nature of curves for other ternary systems are similar to this.

Results and Discussion

Proton-ligand stability constants : In the present work the formation curves ($\bar{n}A$ against pH) for the proton-ligand systems are found to be extended between 0 to 2 on $\bar{n}A$ scale. Thus the dissociation of DHN, DHNSA and CDSA can be represented as :

Fig. 1. Titration curves for $[\text{Sm(III)(CyDTA)(DHNSA)}]$ at 25° , and at $\mu=0.1 M$ (NaClO_4).
 Curve (A) Acid titration curve.
 (B) Secondary ligand titration curve.
 (C) Primary complex titration curve.
 (D) Mixed ligand complex curve.

The values obtained for practical proton ligand stability constants calculated by the method of interpolation at various $\bar{n}A$ values are tabulated in Table 1. All the values are found to be in good

TABLE 1—PROTON LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF SECONDARY LIGANDS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

System	Constant	Temp., $^\circ\text{C}$		
		5	25	45
H-DHN*	$\log K_1^H$	12.46	12.30	12.08
	$\log K_2^H$	10.08	9.85	9.62
H-DHNSA	$\log K_1^H$	11.65	11.41	11.25
	$\log K_2^H$	8.51	8.22	8.02
H-CDSA	$\log K_1^H$	12.56	12.38	12.16
	$\log K_2^H$	7.80	7.62	7.52

* Experiments in 50% dioxane-water medium.

agreement with the values calculated by other reported methods⁹. The error limits are ± 0.05 and ± 0.07 for $\log K_1^H$ and $\log K_2^H$, respectively.

Stability constants of ternary complexes: The mixed ligand system curves (Fig. 1) show that in the case of primary complex curve there is a lowering of pH indicating that primary complex formation is complete upto pH ~ 3.5 . This value of $\bar{n}$ remains almost constant upto pH ~ 10.5 indicating the higher stability of the primary complex. Primary complex curve (C) and mixed complex curve (D) overlap each other at low pH. This indicates that in the pH range where primary ligand combines with metal, combination of secondary ligands does not take place. Since the dissociation of DHN, DHNSA and CDSA is negligible at low pH, the curves C and D overlap. In case of these ligands, curve D diverges from curve C after pH ~ 6.0 . Combination of secondary ligand with primary complex takes place in this range.

Since the dissociation of primary complex does not take place in the range of dissociation of secondary ligand, it can be considered that the secondary ligand combines with primary complex just as it does with $[\text{M(aq)}_n]^{s+}$ in binary systems. In presence of secondary ligands, formation of $[\text{M(III)(A)(OH)}_n]$ is suppressed. The horizontal distance between curve A and curve B can be measured and subtracted from the horizontal distance between curve C and curve D and used for calculation of $\bar{n}$, as reported earlier⁹. A typical plot for $\bar{n}$ against pL for $[\text{Sm(III)-(CyDTA)(DHNSA)}]^{s-}$ system is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Formation curves of $[\text{Sm(III)(CyDTA)(DHNSA)}]$ complex at three different temperatures and at $\mu=0.1 M$ (NaClO_4).

The values of $\log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{CyDTA}}$ at three different temperatures and at $\mu=0.1 M$, with error limit ± 0.08 , have been given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF MIXED LIGAND CHELATES AT $\mu=0.1 M$ AND THREE DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

System	log K_{MAL}^{MA} at °C		
	5	25	45
[Nd(III)(CyDTA)(DHN)] ^{1-}	6.19	5.97	5.75
[Sm(III)(CyDTA)(DHN)] ^{1-}	6.35	6.13	5.95
[Gd(III)(CyDTA)(DHN)] ^{1-}	6.65	6.38	6.10
[Ho(III)(CyDTA)(DHN)] ^{1-}	7.07	6.74	6.38
[Nd(III)(CyDTA)(DHNSA)] ^{1*-}	5.91	5.69	5.46
[Sm(III)(CyDTA)(DHNSA)] ^{1*-}	6.12	5.87	5.64
[Gd(III)(CyDTA)(DHNSA)] ^{1*-}	6.43	6.08	5.79
[Ho(III)(CyDTA)(DHNSA)] ^{1*-}	6.65	6.38	6.10
[Nd(III)(CyDTA)(CDSA)] ^{1*-}	6.75	6.45	6.19
[Sm(III)(CyDTA)(CDSA)] ^{1*-}	6.93	6.64	6.35
[Gd(III)(CyDTA)(CDSA)] ^{1*-}	7.15	6.81	6.41
[Ho(III)(CyDTA)(CDSA)] ^{1*-}	7.69	7.42	7.15

* Experiments in 50% dioxane-water medium.

The order of stability constants of mixed ligand complexes with change in secondary ligands is CDSA > DHN > DHNSA. As ternary systems containing DHN as secondary ligands have been investigated in 50% water-dioxane medium, it will not be appropriate to compare the stabilities of their mixed chelates. All these secondary ligands form five membered ring through two phenoxide ions. The stabilities of mixed chelates are also dependent on the basicity of ligands.

The relative order of stability in terms of metal ions is Ho(III) > Gd(III) > Sm(III) > Nd(III) which may probably be due to decreasing ionic radius

and increasing charge/radius ratio. Similar trend of stability with various rare earths have been reported earlier⁷⁻⁹

In the case of rare earth CyDTA, the ligand occupies six coordination positions of trivalent rare earths and so it is quite possible that the mixed complexes display a higher coordination number of the metals.

Acknowledgement

Thanks of the authors are due to C.S.I.R., New Delhi for the award of a Research Fellowship to (D.G.M.).

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